

Do migration policies work?

Exploring the role of migration policies on migration and migrant integration dynamics

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KEY FINDINGS

- Although several studies confirm that restrictive migration policies decrease migration flows and affect their skills composition, there are also unintended consequences, such as the encouragement of irregular movements.
- Migration policies can also be used as a tool for migrant selection. They can be more restrictive towards specific groups.
- Although skill or quality-selective policies seem to affect the skill composition and volume of skilled migration, their impact can be limited on the volume of skilled migration.
- Skill-selective policies should not be exclusionary of other prospective migrants seeking protection or better living conditions, otherwise they produce the same (side) effects as restrictive policies.
- Restrictive migration and migrant integration policies create a ‘vicious circle’ of exclusion that reinforces fear and separation, while inclusive policies create a ‘virtuous circle’ of integration that promotes openness and interaction.
- Under inclusive policies, the public feels less fear of migrants, while migrants enjoy greater opportunities to participate in society.
- Policies encourage migrants to make investments in their long-term skills, even if this may temporarily retard their participation in the labour market.
- The policy framework is critical in alleviating or removing general institutional barriers and in overcoming general challenges that migrants face in the receiving society, such as discrimination, language barriers, and health issues.
- Anti-discrimination policies crosscut all integration areas and their impact is broadscale.

The number of international migrants is estimated to be almost 272 million globally, comprising 3.5% of the world’s population. Furthermore, the number of internationally displaced persons reached a record number of 26 million in 2019,¹ including over 4 million asylum seekers, and the number of refugees under UNHCR’s mandate doubled between 2013 and 2020. Many factors contribute to the initiation and perpetuation of (forced or voluntary) migration to destination countries over time, and influence the integration of migrants in destination societies. Migration and migrant integration dynamics emerge as an interaction between structural factors (e.g., economic context and policies), formal and informal institutions and individual agency (e.g., human capital and social capital).

ABSTRACT

Migration policies have a long-lasting impact on democratic societies. The openness or closedness of migration policies influences the number of migrants, their characteristics, and their integration outcomes. This policy brief discusses the effects of migration policies on migration trends and integration outcomes and outlines relevant recommendations for the promotion of more effective and evidence-based migration policies.

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¹ International Organisation of Migration, IOM. (2020). World Migration Report 2020. Geneva: IOM.

Among these factors, the migration policies of the destination countries play a role: the openness or closedness of migration policies influences the number and characteristics of migrants arriving to a country and of the migrant population already in a country. Policies also affect integration outcomes of migrants and the likelihood that they will stay in that country.

Migration policies have a long-lasting impact on democratic societies. The recent pushbacks at the EU's external borders, the rise in migration control within the EU and open doors for the inflows of refugees fleeing the war in Ukraine call the effectiveness of current restrictive migration policies in Europe into question. Such policies and practices have not managed to deter migrants looking for better living conditions or protection. Instead, they can cause more human rights violations. Based on the findings of a recent [report](#)² on the link between migration policies and dynamics, this policy brief outlines the effects of policies on migration trends and integration outcomes. Policy-makers can identify areas to address, policy gaps and needs as identified by this review. This brief also presents specific recommendations to national-level policymakers and the European Union on how to make more welcoming migration policies for more effective outcomes.

The effect of policies on migration trends

Risks and side effects of restrictive migration policies

Policies may influence both the overall volume of migration flows and the composition of migrant flows (e.g., in terms of skills, age or national origin). However, a consensus on the influence of migration policies is far from being reached. Over past decades, several migration scholars have argued that there is a gap between the objectives of restrictive migration policies and their observed outcomes. It has been argued that international migration is primarily driven by other factors, such as labour market imbalances, inequalities in wealth, and political conflicts in origin countries; factors on which migration policies have marginal impact. On the other hand, this sceptical view contrasts with that of other researchers, who point out that migration policies have been increasingly effective in influencing the magnitude and composition of migration flows.

Restrictive migration policies decrease migration flows, especially in the field of asylum policies, family migration policies, and visa policies. However, this restrictiveness has some unintended effects, such as discouraging return migration and encouraging irregular movement, increasing permanent settlements among some migrant groups, and increasing tendency towards alternative and some-

times risky migration channels. Particularly interesting is the evidence that more restrictive admission policies and increased border enforcement efforts tend to produce an increase in the number of undocumented migrants, which is exactly what those policies aim to reduce.

Changing realities in the implementation of selective migration policies

Policies can be used as a tool for migrant selection. In other words, policies can be more restrictive towards specific groups, such as irregular migrants and people joining their families, and can also be less restrictive towards high and low skilled migrants.

Skill selective policies have been increasingly popular among destination countries worldwide. A growing number of countries tend to screen potential migrants according to their observable characteristics, such as education and language ability. For example, the EU has introduced [EU Blue Card](#) to give highly-qualified workers from outside the EU the right to live and work in an EU country, provided they have higher professional qualifications. In addition, as part of the comprehensive approach to migration set out in the [pact on migration and asylum](#), the Commission has recently proposed revising the [single permit directive](#) to have a streamlined procedure for the single permit for combined work and residence, which will make the process quicker and easier for applicants and employers. Following the [launch](#) of Talent Partnerships in June 2021 the Commission is now proposing a number of steps to operationalise them, with the aim of agreeing on the first Talent Partnerships by the end of 2022, to make the EU more attractive for non-EU nationals looking for opportunities and to help employers find the talent they need. In addition to these observable characteristics, evidence highlights the importance of unobservable characteristics - such as ability, motivation, or soft skills - in increasing the effectiveness of selective migration policies in improving the quality of migrants. Evidence³ also suggests that the impact of quality selective policies can be limited on the volume of skilled migration due to the role of several other factors (e.g., migration networks, contiguous borders, and a common language) that contribute to perpetuating low-skilled migration flows.

Although states, in principle, have the right to take skill into consideration in favour of selecting one prospective migrant over others, skill selective policies should not override states' duty to welcome other prospective migrants seeking protection or better living conditions (e.g. refugees and family migrants). Indeed, these skill selective policies should not be used as a way of limiting acceptance of other prospective migrants, otherwise

2 Solano, G., Yilmaz, S., & Huddleston T. (2022). The link between migration policies and migration and migrant integration dynamics. An overview of the existing literature (Deliverable 8.1). Leuven: HumMingBird project 870661 – H2020.

3 Czaika, M., & Parsons, C. R. (2017). The Gravity of High-Skilled Migration Policies. *Demography*, 54(2), 603-630.

selective policies may produce the same (side) effects as restrictive policies.

Table 1. Key messages and recommendations on migration policies

Key messages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Restrictive migration policies have adverse effects, such as discouraging return migration and encouraging irregular movements, and increasing tendency towards alternative migration channels. ▪ The impact of quality-selective policies is limited on the volume of skilled migration. ▪ Skill selective policies may produce the same (side) effects as restrictive migration policies do if they limit the acceptance of other prospective migrants.
Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ States should understand the root causes of migration and migratory processes to have more balanced, realistic, and fact-based policy-making and to avoid unintended effects and tendency towards irregular routes. ▪ States should ensure that their skill selective migration policies do not hinder their duty to welcome other prospective migrants, to avoid negative selection and inequalities. ▪ The EU should monitor Member States' practices of restriction on freedom of movement at their external borders and ensure that their actions comply with international and EU human rights law.

The effect of migration policies on integration outcomes

Inclusive policies as promoting skills and a sense of belonging for migrants

Inclusive policies increase the quality of life of migrants. For example, guaranteeing equal rights and implementing targeted policies can positively affect their educational attainment. Inclusive integration policies foster migrants' electoral and non-electoral political participation. Migrants' mental and physical health is affected by a country's integration policies and migrant health policies.

Furthermore, in the legal domain, naturalisation policies have consistently strong and positive effects on migrants' chances of acquiring the nationality of the destination country, which represents a further step towards their full integration in the receiving society.

In the socio-economic domain, under inclusive policies, migrants are more likely to improve their language and professional skills in the country and to secure better jobs in labour markets, and are less likely to be overqualified. Furthermore, labour market integration policies encourage migrants to make investments in their long-term skills, even if participation in these programmes temporarily depresses their participation in the labour market.

Inclusive policies not only increase positive attitudes and interactions between the public and migrants, but also create an overall sense of belonging, trust, and well-being.

Anti-discrimination policies are key factors

Integration policies need to pay attention to all the different areas of integration, in order to ensure access to rights, opportunities and services. The policy framework is critical in alleviating or removing general institutional barriers and in overcoming general challenges that migrants face in the receiving society, such as discrimination, language barriers, and health issues.

Anti-discrimination policies secure greater public awareness of discrimination and greater access to justice for potential victims. These policies seem to have clearer positive effects for working migrants: such effects have been recorded in terms of migrants' income, occupational status, qualifications for their job and ability to relocate for job opportunities. Furthermore, anti-discrimination policies seem to be among those that matter most when considering self-reported poor health and depression.

Benefits for all

As outlined in [Common basic principles for immigrant integration](#) and the [Action plan on integration and inclusion \(2021-2027\)](#), if integration and inclusion are to be successful, there must be a two-way process involving the receiving society, which should create opportunities for migrants' full economic, social, cultural, and political participation. This process must also involve adaptation by migrants, who all have rights and responsibilities in their new country of residence.

Restrictive migration and migrant integration policies create a 'vicious circle' of exclusion that reinforces fear and separation, while inclusive policies create a 'virtuous circle' of integration that promotes openness and interaction. The ways in which governments treat migrants strongly influences how well migrants and the public interact with and think of each other.

A country's overall approach to migration policy is strongly associated with the public's attitude towards migrants. Policies are one of the strongest factors shaping the public's willingness to accept and interact with migrants. Supportive policies and attitudes seem to bring together migrants and non-migrants. Under inclusive policies, migrants and non-migrants generally tend to develop more ideas in common about national identity, patriotism, and social and institutional trust.

Table 2. Key messages and recommendations on migrant integration policies

Key messages
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ The benefit of inclusive policies extends to the non-migrant population and the entire society.▪ Inclusive policies improve the life quality of migrants and their skills and create for them a sense of belonging to the destination society.▪ An effective integration policy embraces all integration areas and recognises their interconnection.▪ Anti-discrimination policies crosscut all integration areas and their impact is broadscale.

Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ States should design inclusive integration policies with the aim of producing tangible advantages for the whole society.▪ States should ensure that integration policies make a strong commitment to creating and/ or opening spaces for meaningful interaction between migrants and receiving communities.▪ States should adopt a comprehensive model of migrant integration and an integrated approach.▪ States should ensure that anti-discrimination policies encompass all integration areas since the principle of equality and non-discrimination is a fundamental pillar in migrants' integration.▪ The EU should provide direct support to Member States to invest in more comprehensive and inclusive integration policies.

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